

Working Memory Architecture and Demand Model - Summary for the General Public

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Working memory (WM) allows us to temporarily hold information “online”, supporting higher cognitive functions such as decision-making, attention, and problem-solving. A key brain region responsible for WM is the prefrontal cortex, an area that differentiates us from other animals. Although our WM resources are limited, it adapts dynamically to the specific demands of different tasks.

Current study uses task-based fMRI data from a large-scale project, the Human Connectome Project, to investigate WM across a range of tasks and conditions. Task-based fMRI measures brain activation during WM tasks, where subjects are asked to recall images presented several trials before.

In our project, statistical and deep learning models acted as “sensors” for task demand and WM activity, predicting how much WM is involved in emotion and language domains. This work provides insights into WM theories from both computational and neurocognitive perspective, with significant implications for education and cognitive rehabilitation.